

Chemical Examination of *Limonia crenulata* Roxb. (Rutaceae)

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Limonia crenulata occurs in Western Himalayas and in the Kumaon region. Leaves of the plant are used in the indigenous system of medicine as a remedy for epilepsy¹. Air dried leaves (2 kg.) were extracted with hot petroleum ether. The extract deposited a green solid (5 gm.) on concentration and cooling. The crude product obtained on washing the solid with excess of petroleum ether had m.p. 85-102°. The crude solid (2.5 gm.) was chromatographed over deactivated alumina using benzene for elution. Evaporation of the eluate and crystallisation of the residue from benzene-petroleum ether gave colourless plates (1.2 gm.), m.p. 105-106°, which was raised to 107° on further crystallisation from methyl alcohol. The total yield of luvangetin was found to be 2.4 gm. (Found C, 69.27, H, 5.39; OCH₃, 12.3; Calc. for C₁₅H₁₄O₄; C, 69.75, H, 5.46, one OCH₃, 12.1%).

The compound gave a red colour with concentrated sulphuric acid, dissolved in hot aqueous alkali giving a yellow solution which remained clear on dilution with water and alkaline alcoholic solutions of the compound also had intense yellow colour indicating that the compound was a coumarin. This was also suggested by its U.V. and I.R. spectra. $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 230 m μ , 260 m μ , and 338 m μ . $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{CHCl}_3}$ 1725 cm⁻¹, 1613 cm⁻¹ and 1575 cm⁻¹.

Analytical values and m.p. corresponded with those of luvangetin. The identity was finally confirmed by comparison with an authentic sample of luvangetin², kindly supplied by Prof. P. K. Bose, Bose Institute, Calcutta.

Singlet 6H (g)	1.7 δ
Singlet 3H (OCH ₃)	4.05 δ
Doublet 1H (e)	5.6 δ
	5.77
Doublet 1H (f)	6.07 δ
	6.24
Doublet 1H (a)	6.24 δ
(J=10 c/s)	6.41
Singlet 1H (c)	6.8 δ
Doublet 1H (b)	7.47 δ
(J=10 c/s)	7.7

1. R. N. Chopra, S. L. Nayar and I. C. Chopra, Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants (C.S.I.R., New Delhi) 1956, 154.

2. E. Späth, P. K. Bose, E. Dobrovolny, A. Mookerjee, *Ber*, 1939, 72, 1450,

It is of interest to record the chemical shifts observed in the n.m.r. spectrum of luvangetin.

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